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Financial preparedness for birth among rural Zambian women Do antenatal care contacts make a difference?

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Introduction: Financial constraints are one of the biggest barriers for women of low-income countries to receive necessary reproductive health services. Educating women about the importance of saving money has been incorporated as a component of antenatal care (ANC) contacts, but little is known whether ANC contacts influence women's saving.</p> <p>Methods: A secondary analysis was conducted on data from a cross-sectional household survey study of 1109 women who recently gave birth in two rural districts of Zambia.</p> <p>Results: Receiving ANC contacts early and often and discussing saving money during ANC were associated with saving money for the mother's birth, but not with saving enough money for the most recent birth.</p> <p>Discussion: Continued effort is needed to encourage women to attend ANC contacts earlier and more frequently. Additionally, the importance of saving money for birth should be discussed during ANC contacts. Future studies need to explore why women's action in saving does not necessarily lead to saving enough for childbirth.</p>	

July 9, 2020
Timothy De Ver Dye, PhD
Editor in Chief
Maternal and Child Health Journal

Title: Financial preparedness for birth among rural Zambian women: Do antenatal care contacts make a difference?

Dear Dr. De Ver Dye.

We are very pleased to have the opportunity to revise our original manuscript for publication in *Maternal and Child Health Journal*. We have addressed each of the reviewer's suggestions and made the necessary revisions and modifications. The table below shows all the comments from the reviewer and the changes made accordingly. We look forward to receiving your additional feedback and are standing by for any further questions.

Sincerely,
The Authors.

Comment	How it was addressed	Page #, Line #
Provide a bit more context in the introduction on the purpose of discussing finances antenatally at all. It is a component of the Centering curriculum as well. It makes logical sense that finances are a part of anticipatory guidance on the transition to parenthood, but not sure if there is any evidence that drives the curriculum	Additional explanation regarding the purpose of discussing finances during ANC contacts added to the introduction.	Page 1 line 22 -page 2 32
Provide greater context on the consequences if have not saved enough. As mentioned, food, facility use and delivery supplies are areas that patients need money for. Are they denied services if they are unable to pay for those things?	The association between financial resources and utilization of a number of reproductive health services added in the introduction.	Page 1 line 8 – line 14
Is it ever the situation that patients choose not to delivery at a hospital as a result?	Additional explanation added to the introduction.	Page 1 line 8 – line 14
Is there significant debt accrued from pregnancy and delivery?	Additional explanation added to the introduction.	Page 1 line 14- line 20
What about the costs of life after the baby is born? Is this typically discussed in antenatal care. i.e. baby clothing, diapers, formula, medications? Or is this typically covered or cultural differences account for the fact that these are not expensive cost items like in higher income countries?	While the cost of life after the baby is not as significant as in higher income countries, it still a burden for women with limited financial resources. Benefit of financial saving for after childbirth briefly mentioned in the manuscript due to the scope/focus of the paper.	Page 4 line 85- line 88
Looking at Table 1: Do you have more refined data to demonstrate any potential lag in decisions to save or	Addressed in the results and discussion section.	Page 3 line 56-63; page 4 line 78-79

<p>initiating saving activity. It seems that the majority of women do not begin saving until the 2nd trimester, which is also when most women initiate care. So there may in fact not be a delay at all.</p>		
<p>Again, what are the consequences of not having saved enough? Why is saving such an important behavior?</p>	<p>Addressed in the discussion section</p>	<p>Page 4 line 82- 87</p>

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Financial preparedness for birth among rural Zambian women:

Do antenatal care contacts make a difference?

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FINANCIAL PREPAREDNESS FOR BIRTH AND ANTENATAL CARE CONTACTS

Abstract

Title: Financial preparedness for birth among rural Zambian women: Does antenatal care contacts make a difference?

Introduction: Financial constraints are one of the biggest barriers for women of low-income countries to receive necessary reproductive health services. Educating women about the importance of saving money has been incorporated as a component of antenatal care (ANC) contacts, but little is known whether ANC contacts influence women's saving.

Methods: A secondary analysis was conducted on data from a cross-sectional household survey study of 1109 women who recently gave birth in two rural districts of Zambia.

Results: Receiving ANC contacts early and often and discussing saving money during ANC were associated with saving money for the mother's birth, but not with saving enough money for the most recent birth.

Discussion: Continued effort is needed to encourage women to attend ANC contacts earlier and more frequently. Additionally, the importance of saving money for birth should be discussed during ANC contacts. Future studies need to explore why women's action in saving does not necessarily lead to saving enough for childbirth.

Key words: Africa, antenatal care, financial barrier, reproductive health, saving for birth

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Significance

What is already known?

One of the biggest barriers for women from low-income countries to access necessary reproductive health services is money. Antenatal care contact are great opportunities to encourage women to start saving money for childbirth. However, limited studies examine how ANC contacts can influence women's saving behavior.

What this study adds?

Early and frequent ANC contacts and money saving discussion during ANC contacts positively influence women's saving behavior, but there may be barriers to women saving enough money in preparation for child birth.

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Introduction

Zambia, like most other sub-Saharan African countries, suffers from high maternal deaths with a maternal mortality ratio (MMR) of 224 deaths per 100,000 live births (World Health Organization [WHO], 2015). Significant barriers for rural women living in rural areas in accessing care still exist despite the abolition of user fees and high informal costs involved in seeking, reaching and receiving reproductive health services (RHS), such as costs for transportation, food, facility use, and delivery supplies (Masiye, Chitah, & McIntyre, 2010). When women are not able to prepare the necessary items such as food and delivery supplies, they often feel embarrassment or shame and are afraid of being scolded and mistreated by the healthcare personnel (Sacks et al., 2017). Furthermore, lack of financial resources is frequently identified as a deterrent for accessing necessary reproductive health services such as ANC contacts, postnatal care contacts, family planning interventions, and facility-based birth (Borgh, Ensor, Somanathan, Lissner, & Mills, 2006; Moyer & Mustafa, 2013; Sacks et al., 2017, Sibanda, Bernays, Weller, Hakim, & Cowan, 2018). Poor people living in rural areas are especially vulnerable because they have limited access to cash and live farther away from health facilities (Borgh et al., 2006). Time spent looking for money such as borrowing money from other people or selling assets to acquire cash can delay the decision to seek and receive care (Thaddeus & Maine, 1994). Moreover, when people have to borrow from a money lender or relatives, exorbitantly high interest rates can further push the family into deeper poverty (Borgh et al., 2006). Therefore, women with fewer financial resources living in rural areas are more likely to bear the burden of preventable maternal deaths and morbidity compared to those with greater financial resources (Jennings, Yang, Otupiri, Akinlo, Okunlola, & Hindin, 2017).

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While in theory, nine months of pregnancy should be long enough for women to save money for childbirth, factors such as low household income, unpredictability of birth outcomes, and men's control over finances can deter women from saving for birth (Jennings, Yang, Otupiri, Akinlo, Okunlola, & Hindin, 2016). For this reason, the WHO recommends couples begin setting aside money early in pregnancy in preparation for birth (JHPIEGO 2004; Jennings et al., 2017; WHO, 2006). Antenatal care (ANC) contact, which include various screenings and education that are crucial for healthy pregnancy and delivery, is a prime opportunity to emphasize the importance of saving (Jennings et al. 2017). However, limited studies examine how ANC contacts can educate and encourage women to financially prepare for childbirth. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between ANC contacts and women's saving behavior and saving enough money for birth.

Methods

Sample

A secondary analysis was conducted using data from a parent study that assessed the impact of a maternity waiting home (MWH) intervention on reproductive health service access and maternal health outcomes in Zambia. The parent study used a multistage random sampling method to collect a cross-sectional quantitative survey. A sample of 1,109 women from the Lundazi and Mansa districts was used for the present study. Details regarding the sampling procedure are published elsewhere (Scott et al., 2018).

Analysis

The data were analyzed using Stata 15.0 (StataCorp, College Station, TX, USA). The independent variables include: 1) the number of ANC contacts, 2) trimester women first enrolled in ANC, and 3) whether saving money for birth was discussed during ANC contacts. Dependent

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variables were 1) saving money and 2) saving enough money for birth. Whether women saved enough money was depended on on each woman's subjective answer based on her own perception of whether she saved enough or not for birth. Demographic characteristics including age, marital status, head of household, number of live births, education level, last delivery location, saving at a bank, owning a bank account, and women's belief about the importance of saving for birth, were examined and adjusted. Variables were selected based on other studies which identified these to be predictors of birth preparedness (Hailu, Gebremariam, Alemseged, & Deribe, 2011; Miltenburg et al., 2015). Descriptive statistics and multiple binary logistic regression models were used to estimate the odds ratio and adjusted odds ratio with 95% confidence intervals. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographics and ANC characteristics are presented in Table 1. More than half of the women attended four or more ANC contacts throughout their pregnancy (59.4%), enrolled in ANC during the second trimester (51.2%), and the majority of them had discussions about saving money (95.5%) with healthcare providers during ANC contacts. A vast majority of the women (83.6%) saved for birth and more than half (57.1%) perceived the money they saved was enough. Of the women who saved money during pregnancy, a little less than half started to save during the second trimester (44.8%) and identified their husband/ partner (62.2%) and parent/grandparent (11.5%) as the most common contributors of the saving.

Antenatal care frequency (OR:1.52; CI:1.10 - 2.10) and discussion about saving money during ANC contacts (OR: 2.65; CI:1.30-5.39) were positively associated with saving money for birth. Attending the first ANC contacts in the third trimester (OR:0.45; CI:0.23-0.90) was negatively associated with saving in the bivariate analysis. However, money saving discussions

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69 during ANC contacts (AOR: 2.57; CI:1.13-5.83) was the only variable shown to be significantly
70 associated with saving money after adjusting for other demographic characteristics. None of the
71 ANC variables were associated with saving enough for birth. Details of the logistic regression
72 models are shown in Table 2.

Discussion

74 The results found that women who attended four or more ANC contacts, attended their
75 first ANC contacts in the first or second trimester, and had money saving discussion during ANC
76 contacts were significantly more likely to save. The positive correlation between the frequency
77 and initiation of ANC contacts and women's saving behavior may be due to the early and
78 frequent exposure to pregnancy related topics, motivating women to financially prepare for birth.
79 The majority of the women attended their first ANC and started to save during their second
80 trimesters, which also suggests the positive influence of ANC contacts and saving. Having
81 money saving discussions alone during ANC contacts was shown to be significant when adjusted
82 for covariates, which suggests that more emphasis needs to be given about the importance of
83 saving during ANC contacts. While the 2016 WHO guideline for ANC increased the number of
84 ANC contacts from four to eight, there is no specific guidelines for health care providers to
85 educate and encourage women to financially prepare for birth. Early and frequent emphasis to
86 save money specifically for birth can encourage pregnant women to financially prepare for birth,
87 allowing them to receive fundamental reproductive health services before, during and after child
88 birth.

89 While all the ANC variables were correlated with saving for birth, none of them were
90 correlated with saving enough money for birth. This finding suggests that while frequent and
91 early attendance of ANC and having money saving discussions may teach women about the

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92 importance of saving money and encourage them to save, there may be other barriers to women
93 saving enough money. There is a need for future studies to examine how saving discussions are
94 led, the disconnect between saving money but not being able to save enough money, and creative
95 interventions to bridge the gap.

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Table 1 Demographics and antenatal care characteristics (n=1109)

Characteristic	N (%)	Characteristic	N (%)
Age		Believe saving is important	
15-19	187 (16.9%)	No	16 (1.4%)
20-24	386 (34.8%)	Yes	1090 (98.3%)
25-29	209 (18.8%)	ANC frequency	
30-34	166 (15.0%)	Less than 4	448 (40.4%)
35-39	95 (8.6%)	4 or more	659 (59.4%)
> 40	61 (5.5%)	Missing	2 (0.2%)
Missing	5 (0.5%)	When in women went for first ANC	
Marital status		0-3 months	478 (43.1%)
Never married	32 (2.9%)	4-6 months	568 (51.2%)
Married/ Cohabiting	1017 (91.7%)	7-9 months	50 (4.5%)
Divorced/ Separated/	60 (5.4%)	Missing	13 (1.2%)
Widowed		Money saving discussion	
Head of Household		No	37 (3.3%)
Women	150 (13.5%)	Yes	1059 (95.5%)
Other	958 (86.4%)	Missing	13 (1.2%)
Missing	1 (0.1%)	Saved for birth	
Relationship to the head of house		No	179 (16.2%)
Other	102 (10.6%)	Yes	927 (83.6%)
Partner/Spouse	857 (89.4%)	Missing	3 (0.3%)
Number of live births		Saved enough for birth	
0-1 child	238 (25.5%)	No	293 (26.4%)
2-3 children	347 (31.3%)	Yes	633 (57.1%)
4-5 children	276 (24.9%)	Missing	183 (16.5%)
5 or more children	202 (18.2%)	Gestational age started to save	
Missing	1 (0.1%)	0-3 months	243 (21.9%)
Education Level		4-6 months	497 (44.8%)
None	182 (16.4%)	7-9 months	185 (16.7%)
Primary	726 (65.5%)	Missing	184 (16.6%)
Secondary	198 (17.9%)	Who contributed to saving	
Missing	3 (0.3%)	Husband/	690 (62.2%)
Last delivery location		Partner	
Home/ Others home/	207 (18.6%)	Children	4 (0.4%)
On the Road		Parent/	127 (11.5%)
Health facility/	853 (76.9%)	Grandparent	
Hospital		Other family	34 (3.1%)
Missing	49 (4.4%)	member	
Ever saved money in bank		Friend	7 (0.6%)
No	1058 (95.4%)	Others	9 (0.8%)
Yes	47 (4.2%)	Nobody	18 (1.6%)
Missing	4 (0.4%)		

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Household has bank/savings account	
No	986 (88.9%)
Yes	48 (4.3%)
Missing	75 (6.8%)

ANC: Antenatal care

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Table 2 Unadjusted and adjusted odds ratios for saving money and saving enough money

	Saved for birth (n=927)		Saved enough for birth (n=633)	
	OR	AOR	OR	AOR
	(95% CI)	(95% CI)	(95% CI)	(95% CI)
ANC frequency				
Less than 4	–	–	–	–
4 or more	*1.52 (1.10- 2.10)	1.05 (0.71-1.56)	1.19 (0.89-1.58)	1.02 (0.73-1.43)
Gestational age at first ANC visit				
0-3 months	–	–	–	–
4-6 months	0.79 (0.56-1.1)	0.86 (0.58-1.28)	0.76 (0.57-1.01)	0.92 (0.66-1.26)
7-9 months	*0.45 (0.23-0.90)	0.73 (0.29-1.81)	0.72 (0.35-1.45)	0.84 (0.37-1.92)
Money saving discussion				
No	–	–	–	–
Yes	*2.65 (1.30-5.39)	*2.57 (1.13-5.83)	0.68 (0.27-1.73)	0.48 (0.17-1.34)

*p<.05 ANC: Antenatal care OR: Odds ratio; AOR: Adjusted odds ratio; CI: Confidence interval; Analyses estimating adjusted odds ratio's (AOR) control for age, marital status, head of household, number of live births given, education level, last delivery location, ever saving money at a bank, owning a bank or savings account, and whether the women thought saving for birth is important. Sample sizes vary due to missing data.